

WAYS TO BUILD THE STUDENT'S ABILITY TO ANALYZE ARTISTIC WORKS

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ABSTRACT

This in the article general education school in students artistic works analysis to do ability formation ways , this the process done in raising different of methods importance about word goes _ In this Uzbek _ and the world literature samples appeal will be done.

Three articles talk about the ways of analyzing the ability of artistic works in secondary school students, the importance of different methods in the implementation of this process. Please refer to examples of Uzbek and world literature.

Today, in continuous education, the development of the future person's oral and written speech, independent and critical thinking, able to understand the cause-and-effect relationships between things and events, not to be confused in the face of life's difficulties, to find a suitable solution to the problems encountered. It is important to form an educated person with all human characteristics. This result can be achieved by forming the ability of students to analyze works of art. This process gives the student the opportunity to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in everyday life.

Literature textbooks of general education schools contain information about the life and work of representatives of Uzbek and world literature, and examples of their works. However, not all students find each introduced work of art with great interest after the lesson and do not try to read its full text, or just glance at the passage given in the textbook and read it to answer when the teacher asks for some information about the work. At this point, it is important to refer to world children's literature in order to attract all students equally to literature, to get aesthetic pleasure from artistic works and to enrich their spirituality. After all, education cannot be carried out without literature, and education cannot be carried out without literature. Of course, organizing such a process very skillfully depends on the teacher, his skills and experience. Because with the help of the teacher, the student learns to analyze the work artistically, dives deeper into the work, learns its true essence, the artistic-aesthetic thinking contained in the work, the power of the word, and becomes a real reader. In fact, reading the work is more important than reading it. Professor A. Rasulov explains this as follows: "In the process of reading and sleeping, the mind takes the lead. More precisely, the

reader becomes a complete receiver and master. To read a work is, in fact, to discover it anew for oneself. Book reader to events interferes, the heroes enliven their words _ _ _ hears, spiritual cases feel from the heart" ¹. If the student work essence understanding skills to literature about competencies if we don't shape it, it's a work not understanding student to the student turns, without learning in training while subject events with Meet the heroes destiny about information only have it will be. Children in literature, as well as adults in literature favorite of heroes images very a lot created _ They are students their own internal world, desires and aspirations, manners and goals with to himself attraction they do their own to his love they deserve it. This heroes honest, brave, unchanging they are own their lives people work and bright the future for good to the road put Tom Sawyer, Temur, Yaramas and Hoshimin, Besh with a child young man (Arif), Shum boy not loving young people to find difficult. Such life-giving, heroic images young generation for imitate sample, torch to be service does They are of children to his companion became many generations in education important role they play today young people their own patriotism and humanities with attraction they do

These days children literature in front serious problems is standing new of technologies intense development as a result of children to study was interest is disappearing. We know that the child to literature forced you can't be interested, you shouldn't be forced by parents or teachers to teach or encourage him to work for grades, but you should do it so that the student comes home in a hurry and learns the textbook on his own let him take it in his hands again and again, let him do his homework wholeheartedly. Also in the textbook given of works complete _ also found a copy by reading try to get out. For this, the process from the appearance of the textbooks to its content, as well as the teacher's own pedagogical skills, to the lesson the child interest for used methods, as well as the teacher and student in cooperation work of analysis interesting and skillfully take It is also important to go. For example, a 5-6 grade student fantasy and to adventures interested yet on the street the ball kicking a walking child. Pick it up, phone and computer games one aside slide the textbook into his hand of removal again one the way textbook pages to the topic according to drawn pictures with is to decorate. This is especially true for 5th, 6th, and 7th graders for very hand will come After all, see also needed through education get can That's it student to the topic adapted the picture watch do it by itself his content complete to understand interested remains. As a result work to the text appeal does

Children in literature problems about when speaking remembering that too tooth must today's in the day to the children themselves to prove, intellectual needs to satisfy and worldview to form service doer children a little bit of journalism limping. Republican children newspaper all the children the same cover can't get That's why for each of our republic in the region region children newspaper, even far away and edge district in the regions district children newspaper organize to do creative children talent manifestation is enough and to them creativity on the way one incentive will be And this own _ in turn the children to literature sincerity to put take will come After all, it is our country edge to edge creativity in the regions doer, him which print to information to give not knowing walked creative

¹ Rasulov A. Criticism, interpretation, assessment. - Tashkent : Science, 2006. - p. 13

children a lot. And so cases literature teacher creative to the student right direction if he gives , next to him calling take his achievement and disadvantages about if you talk, it's real creators , literature lovers of literature enthusiasts growing up to exit the ground prepared would be Also students with together school life, living standing in the area events eg to do worthwhile and remember remains events about publicist article prepare it without pressure release also students social life with to bind , literature science to love , literature his teacher while Appreciate every day the lesson waiting to wait take It's coming. That's it with one in line in students to literature more love to wake up again one method teacher by of the work " advertisement". beautiful by doing is given . Let's say , God gave Tokhtabayev 's life and creativity on the subject lesson during teacher " Five " of the writer with a child young man " , " Yellow giant riding " books to class take Enter the student interesting to show places need If so , read it to give the student from class after this books looking for find it complete by reading to exit encourages . That 's it the work " advertisement". Uzbek and the world in literature another to creators separated lesson use in hours can.

Good we know that different in years school literary in education the world children literature his works to study one how much Methodist scientists and experienced teachers by studied , Antoine Saint Exupery, S. Yesenin, Ernest Seton Thompson, N. Dumbadze It is more practical to observe the works of writers such as If it is assumed that theory and practice require each other, it is desirable to enrich and improve the existing scientific reserve on the problem based on advanced approaches in national and world education.

The teaching of examples of world literature in literary education is not a matter of yesterday or today. Previously, it was studied as examples of world literature or literature of sister nations. In the continuous education system, the teaching of examples of world literature is studied in several directions , starting from primary grades, and in middle and high grades . That is, they consist of examples of folklore of different peoples, literary tales, lyrical poems and prose works. In addition, the composition of world literature consists of the works of Kazakh, Kyrgyz , Karakalpak, Turkmen, and Tajik writers, as well as examples of the art of words of the Greek, English, French, and German peoples. This presents the school teacher with a number of problems that need to be solved. Because, first of all, it is important for the teacher to know and explain to his students why the works of Aesop, Ferdavsi, Shakespeare, Pushkin are studied from world literature, why the works of Chingiz Aitmatov are taught from the lower stages of education.

It can be noted that "Literature" educational programs include the most artistically perfect samples of world literature. Some of them are works that have been meeting the demands of readers with refined tastes for centuries. This is the basis for students to imagine that art, fiction, religion, nation knows no borders. Centuries pass, some people come to this world, but the artistic value of the works that shook the human heart will never lose its influence. The reason for this is that in the works of art he found a vision of the uniqueness and uniqueness of the complex creature called man. Only a reader who has developed the ability to analyze works of art will feel these feelings deeply.

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